

THE PARADOX OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DECISION-MAKING AUTONOMY AND QUALITY ASSURANCE OF EDUCATION

Author(s)*: Liliana AIOANEI

Position: PhD Student

University: "Gheorghe Asachi" Technical University of Iași

Address: Iași, Dimitrie Mangeron Str., No. 67, Romania

Email: liliaioanei@yahoo.com

Abstract

Purpose - The purpose of the article is to define the concept of education management, identifying the relational aspects between the managerial decision and the ethical-moral perspective of autonomy, based on a bibliographic study of recent approaches in the field.

Methodology / approach - The methodological plan of the paper consists in consulting the literature and, based on the bibliographic study, three research directions were established, determining the set of objectives and identifying concepts, methods and methodologies for each of them.

Findings - Following the bibliographic study, in each direction of research, it was observed that the literature has some limitations in the direction of empirical studies on education management, the object of research being treated only theoretically.

Limitations / implications of the research - The limitations of this research consist in the creation of a research methodology, based on the bibliographic study, which will be the basis of the subsequent qualitative and quantitative analyzes.

Practical implications - In the future, the application of the methodology will serve to create a management model that will successfully contribute to the reform process. The pragmatic goal is to determine the methods of increasing managerial performance.

Originality / value - This article highlights the paradox of the relationship between decision-making autonomy and quality assurance in education, because decision-making autonomy can lead to making the right decisions to achieve institutional goals.

Key words: management, quality, education, decision autonom

Introduction

This research proposes, from the epistemic perspective of educational management, an analytical approach on the relationship between decision-making autonomy and achieving the qualitative parameters that the manager of an educational institution must constantly balance by appealing to the system of ethical values. The questions to which we try to answer as up-to-date as possible, refer to: 1.- how active is this relationship in the preschool education system? and 2.- what would be the solution for increasing the degree of autonomy? Destined to elaborate a set of stage conclusions for subchapter III.2 (Research on current trends in the evolution of applied models in Romanian education) the answers to the questions launched will bring their scientific contribution in the elaboration of the doctoral thesis entitled: RESEARCH ON INSTITUTE MANAGEMENT PRESCHOOL FROM ROMANIA IN THE CONDITIONS OF DECISION-MAKING AUTONOMY.

Specialists (Weick & Quin, 1999; Burns, 2005) found that the act generating the autonomy of the decision, although it belongs to the manager, has a limiting framework through the profile of legislative formulations, in which case the size of the manager's creativity is dependent only on professional ethics. For extracurricular activities, the degree of involvement of the local community can influence, through subsidiarity, the decision-making process by calling for consensus and the application of specific ethical principles to education. Following the achievement of the performance criteria, the managers are called

to cultivate values, to activate competences that can offer to the educational unit a well-deserved educational prestige, implicitly social. Therefore, increasing the level of decision-making autonomy implies the integration of management in a new perspective of approaching the problems of modern teaching, in a systematic sense, piloting and strategic innovation, mediating this report so that it generates managerial skills capable of fueling those better autonomous decisions.

From the thematic perspective, the title of this paper is theoretically based on the analytical directions of the research project: 1. establishing a bibliographic reference regarding the autonomy of the decision-making process; 2. researching the decisional particularities in the preschool institutions in correlation with the decisional autonomy; 3. a comparative study between state and private educational institutions by designing a model of correlation analysis with the establishment of comparative criteria (country-EU-USA); 4. designing a model for improving decisions and expanding decision-making autonomy (design, validation, the possibility of implementing the model and establishing evaluation indicators).

The management of education (Landsheere, 1992) through its multiple facets shows its continuous evolution towards synthesis, but also towards the specification on domains and subsystems of education. It remains for the fundamental and applied research, the generalized experience to prove the truth of the hypotheses that are formulated in the field. The requirements of the modern age (Hitt&Middlemist, 1988) demonstrate that management is the effective integration and coordination of resources in order to achieve organizational goals.

The particularities of the educator-leader are not minimized in the scientific management, but on the contrary, they relate to other parameters, content, dimensions, capitalization and training criteria. In a broader context of defining the interdisciplinary and integrative character of pedagogy, we have inserted the problems of designing and achieving education on such a foundation because the design and optimal realization of the instructive-educational activity depend on the way the methods, means and effective organization are articulated. of the didactic approach. The didactic methods, the level of professional competence of those who appeal to them, presenting them in an innovative way, the specialized contents represent ways that lead to the assimilation of models, legalities, descriptions and interpretations as close as possible to reality and with great relevance. psycho-pedagogical. In the conditions in which social shocks appear, events that change, major social ruptures, another type of learning is needed, the so-called innovative learning, in which certain experiences are recorded. The quality of the pedagogical act must be decisive for the effort to balance the relationship with the decisional autonomy. The social imperative of increasing the quality of education is the one that proposes as a solution to increase the level of decision-making autonomy, achievable by determining the decision-makers to trigger what private schools have already started, respectively capitalizing on higher educational traditions and models of the Romanian interwar school whose customary depository and beneficiary is and must be the community.

As far as we are concerned, only at the community level there is a relative stability, including in terms of ethical constancy supported by a system of moral values, although there are different positions generated by the level of education and comprehensibility of parents' relationships with school.

Among the theoretical principles that guide and substantiate educational management are recognized democratic leadership, combining leadership and sole responsibility (unipersonal) with leadership and collective responsibility, promoting leadership based on competence, efficiency and deontology of leadership. Given the requirements of civil society, democracy and the rule of law, the management of education must be carried out, therefore on a democratic basis. This principle implies that for the implementation of a decision it is required to consult the echelons subordinated to the management and through them and the executors of the decisional act, so as to form an interactive management based on the realization of organizational and decisional structures of education that combine, in a balanced and harmonious way, the directing the unidirectional vertical from the central level with the directing in the network, horizontally, at the intermediate and local level of the educational institutions, wishing to eliminate any administrative-bureaucratic elements towards the development of specific structures of democracy. This ensures the proper functioning of education in a democratic spirit and its inclusion on European coordinates, with all the favorable consequences arising from them. We emphasize that this would have implicitly manifested the right of education and its representatives to anticipation and opposition, reconstruction and contestation.

Through a new legislative basis, in the corpus of expectations and pedagogical norms or in the transmitted contents, the educational unit should acquire the right to make changes in the curricular plan

by operating a selection, a decantation, a hierarchy according to criteria that have in view of the pedagogical relevance of the set of knowledge inserted in the pedagogical exercise. through this, quality becomes a dynamic element of professional ethics, being, as previously mentioned, the "interface" that relates to the children's parents, to the public opinion in general. The English jurist Jeremy Bentham (1748-1832) was the first to introduce public opinion into the equation of ethics. In *An Introduction to the Principles of Morals and Legislation*, published in 1781, the English jurist Jeremy Bentham raised the issue of the moral essence that must underpin any principles of civil law, which he called private distributive law. Therefore, in the effort to optimize the educational management process as an art of leadership (with its entire causal chain involving processualism, decision management and optimization, complexity of organizing the organization and evaluating efficiency, etc.) all stages and functions acquire notable defining values. when it conceptualizes this activity as a set of principles and laws, of norms (ethical, moral) elaborated in order to govern the educational act in principle plan and regulates the decisional act. In making a decision, the most important element of its functional scheme is managerial experience, as stated by the representatives of the school of human relations management (Douglas McGregor, Michael A. Hitt, Denis R. Middlemist, Abraham Maslow, Elton Mayo, Kurt Lewin, FR Roethlisberger, Frederick Hertzberg, Rensis Likert).

The educational process manifests itself at all levels of the social ethos, as an ontological form of expressing human behavior in different civilizational stages of history, but is objectified as a fundamental effect for determining the evolution of the human being and the effective engagement of man, his personality and his background. in its chronological development through life, knowing that the success, performance and competitiveness of any educational institution, implicitly the preschool, depend largely on management, on "managerial art" (Gerbier, 1993).

The process of decision making in management

The decision as a volitional expression in itself is a deliberate act that involves the rational choice of possible solutions to problems considered optimal, with the intention of achieving the desired effect. Henry Fayol (1966) identifies, in his research of the last century, five functions of management in correlation with the decision-making act, namely: planning, organization, ordering, coordination, control. The decision is the answer to a specific problem and is a social form of validation of an action, through the movement of human, material and financial resources. The decision is efficient, but it first requires an ordering factor, namely efficiently oriented managerial responsibility. It is logical that the efficiency of an organization, its ability to function and, in the current conditions created by the new market economy (even the survival of the institution), depend on the effectiveness of its members, especially the effectiveness of management at all levels.

The decision, without claiming a certain function, represents an essential element, an axis mundis of the managerial activity because as a result of the institutionalized decision-making process it is found in all its functions, representing its instrument of expression by choosing a direction of action (HA Simon, 1960), or implementing a strategy (PC Fishburn, 1970).

Figure 1. Stages of decision making by Herber.A.Simon

Adaptation and integration in the system are dependent on the quality of the decision because it materializes in plan formulas, program outlines or directions, strategic variants. Management, defined by specialists as the art and science of drawing, directing and administering the work of others to achieve set goals (AS Apply, 1969; Ph. Shay, 1967; LJ Kazmier, 1968; Ch. B. Handy, 1977) represents, first of all, a compound of constants of power, authority and influence, which, in order to improve their quality, must be brought to the same table as the official decision-maker. In other words, in order to make institutional decisions, the diameter of the manager's autonomy is directly proportional to the result of an equation in which political-administrative terms, dependence on financial resources within legal limits and ethical-moral openings of the legislative framework are all subject to activity, a decision. In any institution, the proposed objectives, the legal framework and the financial limitations through the amount of information, are linked to a certain context which it explains and through which it determines the decision-making act. (C. Drury, 1992: 236).

The decision - and we refer to the manager's decision - in order to have the efficiency expected by the managerial objectives must meet a series of criteria. Also called rationality requirements, they are:

- I. The legality of the decision, which implies not only its inclusion in the national legislative normative system, but has as a mandatory requirement the fact that the adoption of the act itself must belong to a person invested and empowered with official legal right. That is why it is said that the decision must be empowered by the management body in whose service tasks it is provided;
- II. The scientific substantiation of the decision represents a benchmark, a note of the manager's professionalism - cognitively demonstrable by models, techniques, knowledge, skills - through which it is enhanced to overcome the inherent level of subjectivism and the aspect of ad hoc "improvisation" of the decision-making process, precisely by knowing and applying the mechanisms of the market economy. The level of perception, assimilation, corroboration and analysis of information can ensure the reduction of the level of uncertainty in the formulation and adoption of a decision;
- III. The opportunity of the decision theoretically synthesizes the attribute of institutional self-regulation, the ability to adapt to the influence of endogenous or exogenous disruptive factors that oppose the institution's objectives, and in terms of practical applicability the ability to make decisions in a timely manner, resonating with the institution's objectives. with the actuality of the temporal development of the events (tangible by the immediate connection to niches and opportunities);
- IV. The completeness and wording of the decision, although apparently could be considered only formal requirements, in reality by conciseness and clarity illustrates the cognitive level of the manager, the degree of assimilation of expertise needed to overcome complex issues in order to develop a fully structured, correct and clear formulated in apprehensive terms (proposed objective, mode of action, available resources, allocated resources, decision maker, responsible for implementing the decision, place of application, time and deadline) by clear provisions and objectives, thus able to ensure the success of its implementation at V.- Coordination and integration of the decision, as ways of activating the principle of unity of decision and action, must be done both vertically - by correlating decisions with higher hierarchical levels, and horizontally - when aiming not only the role of manager of insertion in the team of the decision-making act, but especially based on the absolute compatibility as an expression of the horizontal harmonization of the activity of the functional compartments of its component sectors, up to the individual level, through the relations established between the personnel compartments, everything being subscribed, dedicated to achieving an important objective. ;
- V. The decision efficiency belongs temporally to the post-implementation stage, being the functional summative expression of all the previous criteria and expresses as a percentage the level of obtaining the effect related to the invested effort.

Decisional autonomy

Decisional autonomy as a phenomenon, expresses the collaboration of managerial actions that the American Ricky V. Griffin in Fundamentals of Management (2014) shows in the dedicated figure 2.

Figure 2. Managerial control as part of a feedback loop in Griffin's loop

The success, performance and competitiveness of any educational institution, implicitly of the preschool one, largely depend on the management, through the integration and effective coordination of the resources in order to achieve the organizational objectives. (D. Reynolds, R. Bollen, B. Creemers, D. Hopkins, L. Stoll, & N. Lagerweij, 2005) From a decision-making perspective, the competitive advantage of an organization lies in its people and leaders. In this context, it is known that among the organizational indicators is not only the efficiency of preschool management - by streamlining resources and professionalism of teachers - but especially the investment of trust of parents and children, teachers and employees in a successful management team, due, among other things, to the ability to optimize their decisions.

In the effort to optimize the process of educational management as an art of leadership (with its entire causal chain involving process and quality optimization, complexity of organizing the organization and evaluating efficiency, etc.), all acquire notable defining values when conceptualizing this activity as a whole. of principles and laws, of norms (ethical, moral) that govern education in principle and regulate the decisional managerial act. The competitive atmosphere, the dynamic adaptation to the requirements of modern didactics necessarily impose a new model of organization, in a systematic sense, of piloting and strategic innovation.

By applying real decision-making autonomy, the transfer of authority to the base of the hierarchical pyramid can be obtained and we refer here to the transition from central to regional authority and later to the level of educational institutions. The transfer of authority had to be complemented by access to all types of resources (human, financial focused on learning outcomes), the general and financial management being the result of the collaboration between the educational unit and the local community. Teachers would have received increased responsibilities, but also support in their professional development, and directors (managers) would have been hired for a fixed period, conditioned by the performance achieved.

Discussion and conclusions

- a. Education requires from a managerial perspective a scientific, modern substantiation.
- b. At the basis of this substantiation must be, in the last resort, the institutionalized expression of an act of decisional autonomy.
- c. In this complex set, the axiological dosages and readjustments of the decisional autonomy can be made only by those directly involved, effectively in the educational process, by the educators themselves, the proposals being sent to the unit manager also by virtue of the autonomy and action responsibility they should have. and whereby these proposals should be centralized and analyzed.
- d. The ethical and moral values infused in the act of education must keep their true reactive and prospective dimensions in front of the present and the future.

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